

Impact of Outsourced Housekeeping Services on Guest Satisfaction with Respect to Star Hotels

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ABSTRACT

The main goal of Hotel industry business is to meet guests' needs while achieving profit targets. The Guest satisfaction is the very important factor for the Hotel industry. It enhances Hotels' reputation, increases room sales as satisfied guests are more frequent visitor and increases profitability.

Major Star Hotels Outsource Housekeeping services to sustain cost effectiveness, saves time, improves service quality and improves efficiency of department. This study focuses on the impact of outsourced Housekeeping services on guest satisfaction keeping in view the Hotels which are outsourcing Housekeeping services. This study considered the few attributes of Housekeeping staff and Cleanliness of outsourced areas impact on Guest Satisfaction. The data was collected from Guests who stayed in Star category Hotels of Pune.

Keyword: *Guest Satisfaction, Outsourcing, Housekeeping Services*

Introduction:

The main goal of service industry business is to meet guests' needs while achieving profit targets. This customer-orientation is now essential because of the increasing competition and quality requirements (Chikán 1997).

The tourism hotel sector it has been proven that quality leads to both satisfaction (Patterson and Spreng 1997, Caruana, Money, and Berthon 2000, Baker and Crompton 2000, Cronin et al. 2000) and perceived

value (Petrick 2002, Zeithaml 1988, McDougall and Levesque 2000, Sweeney and Soutar 2001). Also in some studies satisfaction has been found to lead to perceived value (Chang and Wildt, 1994; Petrick and Backman, 2002) while in others perceived value has been found to lead to satisfaction (Cronin, Brady, and Huit 2000, Tam, 2000).

The Guest satisfaction is the very important factor for the Hotel industry. It enhances Hotels' reputation, increases room sales as satisfied guests are more frequent visitor and increases profitability.

In this study, the researcher finds the impact of outsourced Housekeeping services on guest satisfaction keeping in view the Hotels which are outsourcing Housekeeping services. This research has been done in continuation to the previous research which was on Outsourcing :A study on benefits to Housekeeping departments in Hotels(Honey Tyagi, Seema Zagade, July 2015).It has been observed through previous researches, Hotels outsource various Housekeeping services to sustain cost effective housekeeping operations, improves quality, efficiency and performance of the department.

The areas which are outsourced in the Housekeeping department are Public area cleaning, Guest laundry & Hotel Laundry, Flower Decoration, Horticulture and landscaping, Façade/Glass cleaning Pest control, Upholstery maintenance, Special cleaning tasks Carpet shampooing, Marble polishing and Garbage Disposal.

It has been observed in the study the Impact of Outsourcing Housekeeping Services is positive on Guests' satisfaction for certain factors and few factors needs improvement.

Objectives

1. To study the impact of Housekeeping Staff attributes on Guest Satisfaction
2. To study the outsourced cleaning areas impact on Guest satisfaction

Literature Review

1. (Fornell1992; Anderson et al.1994; Muffatto and Panizzolo 1995; Sharma et al. 1995; Zeithaml 2000). Satisfaction is a core factor of business success; several key benefits are enumerated for firms. Satisfaction can:

- enhance the company's reputation and positive image
- increase sales volume, satisfied customers are more frequently purchase
- lower marketing costs of attracting new customers
- increase positive word of mouth providing instant awareness and lowering the buyer's risk
- improve more effective respond to customer needs
- lower transaction costs
- reduce the rate and costs of false performance
- fewer resources devoted to handling and managing complaints
- increase the stability of staff
- indicate increased loyalty, loyal customers are likely to continue to purchase from the same supplier
- insulate current customers from competitive efforts causing less churn
- reduce price elasticity, as satisfied customers are willing to pay for the benefits and more likely to be tolerant of increases in prices
- increase profitability and market share lead to better economic returns of investment

(Reichheld and Sasse r 1990; Bátor 2007).

2. (Lovelock and Wright, 1999) the delivery of hotel services involves high contact encounters with significant interaction among customers, staff and facilities.

3. (Aleksandra Pisnik Korda Borut Milfelner,2009) mentioned in their research that perceived value of hotel guests influences hotel guest satisfaction, which mostly leads to guest decision to return to hotel. In

practical terms this means that intelligence about how to add value from the hotel guest's point of view can in the long term lead to higher hotel guest satisfaction. It is however not unimportant that perceived quality not only directly impacts customer satisfaction but that there also exists the indirect relationship through perceived value. Their research results support additional evidence that together with perceived quality also the perceived price is an important predecessor of perceived value in hotel services.

4. (KESH PRASAD, PHILIP W. WIRTZ, LARRY YU 2014) In their study researchers identifies the underlying relationship between guest evaluation of hotel facilities and staff service on the one hand, and perceived value, satisfaction, and intent to revisit and recommend on the other. The results show the direct effects of guest evaluations of staff service quality, guest room quality, security and service problems on value, satisfaction, and intention to revisit and recommend. They mentioned that significant moderating effects affected the guest evaluations of the hotel facilities and staff service quality.

5. Hicks, J. Darrel, 2003 He mentions in the research Cleanliness isn't just about the absence of dirt. How does your facility appear to an outsider? Is it cluttered, dingy, outdated and looking run down? He said that Housekeeping department need to get other departments involved in improving the appearance. The staff needs to work promptly for any maintenance work. One staff to liasion with guests instead multiple. He also mentions in his research paper that staff needs to listen carefully to the customer's complaint. Gather as much information as possible. Make notes and read them back to convey the message that you are actively listening and will do something about the complaint.

6.Honey Tyagi,Seema Zagade (July 2015) Outsourcing is practiced in most of the Hotels to sustain cost effectiveness, improves performance of existing employee, saves time, improves service quality and also improves efficiency of department.

7. Commons (1931), Coase (1937) and Williamson (1975) stated Outsourcing is a widely excepted business tool for achieving business goals. "It is commonly being preferred to use as when in house activities are higher than buying products or services from the market".

8. Momme (2001) indicates different sourcing strategies: make or buy, outsourcing, in-sourcing, and strategic sourcing. The most common types of

outsourcing are traditional and transformational or strategic outsourcing. In general, there exist three main clusters of reasons driving the outsourcing decision – reducing cost, improving operational performance and developing competencies.

4. Research Methodology

Primary Data:

The data required for the research was collected using the following techniques:

Questionnaire: A questionnaire was drafted constituting straight forward and relevant

Questions and circulated over to the Guests' who stayed in star Hotels. The data collected in person and also online.

Sampling: The sample comprised of 60 Guests who stayed in 15 Star category Hotels of Pune, from each Hotel four guests data are collected. These Hotels outsource the Housekeeping services mentioned in this study.

Secondary data

The required secondary data was collected from published journals, online journals, books & internet.

5. Data Analysis

A. Staff Attributes : Impact on Guest Satisfaction

Interpretation:

The Outsourced Housekeeping staff attribute has been observed by guest and also their interaction with guest during their stay, for various Housekeeping services which are outsourced. The attributes which are studied (on the scale of 1 to 5 where 1 is Very Unsatisfied and 5 are Very satisfied), in this research are:

- Courteous:** It has been found that this attribute has a positive impact on guest satisfaction. The Housekeeping staff acknowledges them by wishing as per the time and guests were satisfied by the staff Courtesy.
- Well Groomed:** The staff has been observed for grooming which guest rated them above satisfied. The staff observed was well groomed and this attributes makes a positive impact on guest satisfaction
- Uniform Cleanliness:** The Housekeeping staff Uniforms were observed clean and guest were satisfied with cleanliness of staff Uniform.
- Handling Guest queries-** The guest found satisfied when they had interaction with Housekeeping staff for queries related to housekeeping services.

B. Cleanliness: Impact on Guest Satisfaction

Interpretation:

The guest has rated the satisfaction on the scale of 1 to 5 where 1 is Very Unsatisfied and 5 is Very satisfied for the cleanliness of the above areas in Hotel. The room cleaning is done by inhouse staff of the Hotel which are studied for this research. The other areas which are Bathroom, Restaurants, Lobby, Lifts, Parking, Swimming pool and garden comes in the category of Public Areas which are cleaned by Outsourced Housekeeping staff.

Room cleaning which is done by inhouse Hotel Staff has a very satisfied impact on Guests.

Most of the Public areas which are outsourced for cleaning are found to have positive and satisfied impact on Guest. However, Parking cleanliness impact rating is below satisfied.

6. Recommendation & Suggestions:

As per this research, I would like to recommend the outsourced staff may also have a positive impact on Guest even though they are not Hotel inhouse staff. This positive impact could be the on the various factors of the Outsourced staff being trained well by the agency or they possess good work experience which is not considered in this study.

The parking area has been observed less satisfaction impact on guest due to most accessed area by everyone in Hotel, Hence the Housekeeping department may increase the frequency of cleanliness by outsourced

staff for parking, by doing so this may lead to positive satisfaction on Guest.

7. Conclusions

The findings of the research are :

7.1 This study considered the Housekeeping staff attributes which are Courteous, Well Groomed staff, cleanliness of uniform and handling guest queries impact on Guest Satisfaction. All attributes of outsourced Housekeeping staff have a positive impact on guest satisfaction.

7.2 The cleanliness impact is mostly positive of all public areas except parking area which has less satisfaction.

8. Limitations

The sample of Hotel does not cover entire strata of population of Pune. However, the sample chosen has a combination of various star categories of Hotels. This study is purely based on the information provided by the Guests' of sample hotels. The study is conducted in the current scenario and the opinion, perception and expectations of the respondents may differ with the services provided by the different Outsourced agency.

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